

CIVIC-MINDED LEADERSHIP: PARTICIPATION OF STUDENT LEADERS OF ISABELA STATE UNIVERSITY- CAUAYAN CITY CAMPUS IN CIVIC AFFAIRS

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ABSTRACT

Student leaders have the capacity to guide others in the achievement of the common goal. This led to the purpose of the study which was to determine the engagement of student leaders in civic affairs particularly in their community (local area). The researchers utilized a qualitative research method which involves semi-structured interviews with the ten students who are recognized to hold a position in an organization inside the school, also informed consent was given to the participants in order to gather data concisely and clearly. The results show that the participation of the student leaders in their community are through voting and volunteering. Under the latter, student leaders involved themselves in environmental-related affairs and people's organizations. They were able to incorporate their leadership experiences into civic affairs by taking their time to listen to people's voices and concerns, imparting knowledge, and proposing activities as well. Although they encounter criticism and difficulties in balancing their time between their leadership, civic roles, and family, student leaders are continuously gaining further knowledge and skills in these areas through their exposure to both worlds: school and community. Therefore, active participation of student leaders in civic affairs is seen in this study.

Keywords: *Student Leader, Leadership, Civic Affairs, Civic Participation (Engagement)*

INTRODUCTION

Being a leader is a process, not something that is inherited, and having a civic mind at a young age to which interested in and care about what is going on in his community while being active in educational roles is what our society needs. They are individuals with a determined mentality to escape from what is common and voice out the silent murmuring of others, they are those who have a compassionate heart and a vision to be an agent of change for the betterment of which success does not happen overnight but with diligence and perseverance. That is why student leaders are vital in the development and their participation in civic affairs. Moreover, the special roles they have as a leader at the school level are also an important aspect of knowing how they apply their leadership experiences, their participation in civic affairs, and their responsibility as a citizen. Just as Olorunda (2019) stated, students are supposed to realize their civic rights and responsibilities.

Student leaders have the capacity to guide others in the achievement of the common goal. Additionally, they are not just students but also citizens who must have care and a greater sense of community while they are in their youth. Their participation enhances skill development, confidence, and competency building which is why one must also have a proper pathway in taking part and becoming effective change agents in their communities (Clement et al., 2014). Within the civic engagement and leadership domain, the first pathway is youth-friendly forums. When student leader has knowledge of and access to youth-friendly forums, they are able to discuss and reflect on issues that are important to them. These youth-friendly spaces are an important component of giving student youth leaders a platform for learning about civic issues and engaging with their communities.

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The second pathway that has been identified as a collective voice, according to the program studied by Clement, et al., (2014), notes that an important component of youth becoming change agents is that they utilize youth-friendly spaces to come together to share experiences and viewpoints and work collaboratively to develop a goal or plan of action. The third pathway is collective action. Collective action is about youth advocating for and taking action on the goals and issues that they have identified as important. The study recognizes that the collective action pathway requires that youth student leaders have the skills, knowledge, and confidence to effectively engage with governance structures, community leaders, and public authorities, such as local and central governments. These pathways may guide student leaders in their civic engagement. Embodying the importance of civic engagement opens the doors to many opportunities, unlocking skills and widening one's perspective.

Furthermore, in this context, civic engagement (or participation) is defined by the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) as "individual or collective actions in which people participate to improve the well-being of communities or society in general" (UNICEF, 2020). Traditionally, civic engagement portrays some actions including voting, attending community meetings or functions, contacting public officials, attending protests, signing petitions, or writing articles about one's community (Cho, 2020). Additionally, civic engagement for the student leaders in their community service emphasizes participation in voluntary service to one's local community, this could be a person functioning alone or as a member of a body.

According to the study of Arcega (2017) which focuses on student leaders' volunteerism reviving the Bayanihan spirit, volunteerism is a form of public spirit and civic awareness with elements of dedication, friendship, mutual aid, and progress. With this, student leaders were positive in terms that different activities helped them gain more experience and knowledge, develop their skills, and grow the support system and teamwork. However, student leaders agreed that they encountered different challenges that affected their service to the community. Examples of these are lack of resources, small number of volunteers, lack of communication, and other problems. Other than that, according to a study conducted by DePaul University (2022), most people think of civic engagement as voting or being involved in politics. However, civic life is so much more than that. Active civic engagement produces communities that people want to live in by creating an environment where people are informed about issues and engage with their neighbors in meaningful, respectful, and positive ways.

Student leaders' affairs or duties not only boxed in their active participation in school but also it is a continuous activity and extension of their leadership experiences to their community or within the locality. However, schools specifically Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) have a huge part in cultivating the potential of students. The growth of leadership among students is perceived to be a key goal for any academic institution" (Labor, 2017). In connection with this, universities, especially the public ones, are invited to become leaders in educating for SDGs and in accounting for the results achieved (UNESCO, 2017). Higher education institutions (HEI) play a critical role in developing student leaders equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to mobilize societal changes that the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) call for (Lee, et al., 2022). Student leaders are vital in the advancement of goals this is in connection to SDG 17 (Partnerships for the goals). Their ability to lead inside the school grounds and/or participate in community service like volunteering in local activities such as cleaning drives, communal gardens, and even personal gardens can help promote sustainability and development at the grassroots level.

This was emphasized in the study conducted by Lee, et al., (2022), analyses showed that taking a leadership role in the SDGA empowered students to deepen their engagement with the SDGs and overcome barriers such as lack of knowledge and feelings of powerlessness. Secondary findings showed that community-building, flexibility and a sense of ownership were key strengths of the program and contributed toward student leaders' feelings of hopefulness, self-confidence, and inspiration. This work offers a window into the experiences of student leaders who have worked to advance SDG engagement within their institution. Also, the study suggests that student-led initiatives represent untapped potential for HEIs to prioritize and support to help deliver on their SDG implementation and engagement efforts.

Civic engagement entails active involvement that goes beyond civic consciousness and understanding of civic responsibility, and a civically engaged student leader is needed in a society flooded with various sociopolitical issues. The realm of academia plays a vital role in developing the desire to help, volunteer, and make a difference in the lives of many. Student leaders are often the driving forces to make movements inside the school but are also expected to get involved in civic and service-oriented activities all for the social cause in their respective communities. Through this, this study aims to explore the following: (a) how do the student leaders participate or engage themselves in civic affairs, (b) how do they apply their leadership experiences to civic affairs and/or civic responsibilities within their local communities, and (c) what are the advantages and difficulties of having leadership experiences as they fulfill their civic affairs and/or civic responsibilities.

METHODS

This study implemented a qualitative research approach, which allows qualitative researchers to study people in their natural settings, to identify how their experiences and behavior are shaped by the context of their lives, such as the social, economic, cultural, or physical context in which they live (Hennink, et al., 2020). With this, the researchers employed semi-structured interviews and provided guide questions to track what must be unraveled in this study, these guide questions are answered by the ten (10) identified student leaders from different organizations. In terms of identifying participants, the researchers utilized a purposive sampling technique. The selection of participants or sources of data to be used in a study, is based on their anticipated richness and relevance of information in relation to the study's research questions (Yin, 2011).

Since the researcher's goal is to know the civic-minded leadership participation of student leaders in civic affairs in their locality, the researchers believe that this method is appropriate in choosing the sample for the population and for the research itself. This is to determine if the participants do participate or engage themselves, as well as to unfold what specific civic affairs they get to be involved in within their respective communities. Impart their fulfillment/advantages and difficulties they experience in the journey of their leadership and how they incorporate their leadership experiences as well as act in regards to their civic responsibility/civic affairs. Moreover, to strengthen the reliability of the information gathered, the researchers utilized voice recording and set a letter of consent before the researchers proceeded to interview the participants.

Furthermore, the participants of the study are the ten student leaders from the School of Arts and Sciences Department who were elected and appointed from various organizations. The researcher explained to the participants the importance of their response to the study. The researcher requested the participants to answer with all honesty. After the participants answered the guide questions, the researcher will collect and gather data for interpretation coding was also utilized in this study, just as Bailey (2007) said this is to identify which topics or issues portions of the data refer to and organize the data in a way that is useful for further analysis. With the data gathered, the researchers came up with results and discussion.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, all participants were asked if they are willing to participate in this study, and all of them agreed. Orientation was given to them, wherein the researchers explained the details of the study. After that, informed consent forms were given to them and they voluntarily signed it. The participants' permission was also asked about the recording of their interview proceedings, and they agreed to it. Moreover, the researchers guaranteed the anonymity and confidentiality of their identity and responses which were solely for the purpose of this study only.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ten-valued participants of this study are active leaders in Isabela State University-Cauayan Campus and are currently in the position of the following organizations; Student Body Organization – the central

organization of the School of Arts and Sciences department for its students, Artem Loqui Debate Society – an organization promoting debate as an educational and worthwhile endeavor for students, and Political Science Society is an organization for students of BA Political Science form ISU-Cauayan.

Participation of Student Leaders in Civic Affairs

The involvement of student leaders in civic affairs such as in communal activities and matters of concern will contribute to a major significant and beneficial impact which will give rise to positive effects on the community itself. This is supplemented by Chitiga (2014), continuous effort to give equal emphasis to civic engagement are needed as developing civically-engaged students are a meritorious goal on its own. Based on the research made in this study, nine out of ten student leaders revealed they do participate in civic affairs. They involved themselves in civic affairs specifically through voting and volunteering. Under the latter, student leaders involved themselves in environmental-related affairs and people's organizations such as the LGBTQIA+ Organization for Inclusivity, Gender Equality Advocacy, and Local Youth Development of their local government unit.

Four participants revealed that "voting" is the major civic affair they got participated in as this only took place recently and their first time being part of the electoral process. One of the participants expressed "...as a first-time voter having the privilege and the right to vote I used this opportunity to get involved right away and choose a leader that will lead the country and my town (Participant 1, personal communication, June 12, 2023)." Also, Participant 9 revealed that he became an election poll volunteer last election. It is important for student leaders to exercise their rights and civic duties. This is supported by Blais and Achen (2010) that a sense of citizen duty is a powerful predictor of voter turnout. Other than that, three of the participants hold a position in an organization outside the school focusing on youth community engagement and making a contribution to it. Most of the participants are actively involved in "volunteering" as their way to give and do something for their community to which they reveal that mostly they volunteer in clean-up drives and feeding programs. One of the participants stated, "I'm a volunteer youth teacher and we teach particularly to the elementary pupils (Participant 5, personal communication, June 12, 2023)."

Also, Participant 10 revealed that he is part of Project Bangka in their community in which they give free reading tutorials for children, especially during the pandemic, other than that he is an environmental advocate as he expressed. Supplemented by Arcega (2017), cultivating the spirit of volunteerism in college students and leaders benefits both the individuals and society, and Merza et al., (2022) reported that student leaders in an organization exhibit greater social change engagement than their peers. It postulates that immersion in groups anchored on community service, religion, and justice cultivates students' engagement in societal revolution. On the other hand, one participant revealed the opposite in regards to civic participation stating, "Mostly, I don't participate in our community's affairs actively, I often reflect about this, but I don't really put it to practice (Participant 7, personal communication, June 12, 2023)." In contrast, Hsu (2021) stated that citizen's interest in civic participation tends to motivate young people to engage in political activities and social affairs. Thus, students aren't just for learning, apart from it they are also citizens, a part of society.

Nevertheless, these civic engagements of student leaders display that they make highlight of their youth and a proof that they observed and acted to what their community needs. Such individuals are more interested in what is going on around their surroundings and more likely the concerned citizen in their locality.

Applying Leadership Experiences to Civic Affairs

Being a leader is a process, not something that is inherited. Student leaders' capability, and capacity to handle situations, are shaped by their experiences at the school-based leadership level which they can apply and use to fulfill their civic affairs. Provided here are the leadership experiences of student leaders as they fulfill civic affairs.

As one of the participants expressed "...taking time to listen to other people's suggestions, concerns, and situations in order to address and solve the problem in the community (Participant 1, personal communication,

June 12, 2023).” From school to community students were able to apply their sensitivity to people’s voices and concerns. The idea of being a civic leader allows us to ask how we can create change and progress in our communities (Matkin, et al., 2023). In addition, a participant stated, “I exercise my leadership experiences through imparting knowledge – communicate uprightly in order to maintain unity and able to work hand-in-hand to meet what is needed to fulfill in the community (Participant 2, personal communication, June 12, 2023).” These results represent the seven (7) answers of the participants. Participant 6 expressed that through proposing activities in their barangay she is able to engage and Participant 8 used to help with their officials in the community. This is supported by Clemente (2014) in his study in which within the civic engagement and leadership domain, the first pathway is youth-friendly forums. When student leader has knowledge of and access to youth-friendly forums, they are able to discuss and reflect on issues that are important to them.

Moreover, researchers also asked the student leaders what civic responsibilities they are liable to fulfill, and the result revealed that they have to encourage youth to be registered voters as a step to make a real change and to be active citizens (driven also by their course) and take part in the community’s concerns as well as abide by the community’s rules and laws as a common citizen in the community. The academe is a sculptor of civic engagement among students. Giving them opportunities for dialogue, reflection, and community involvement spring civic engagement. The exposure to school-based advocacy, inclusive teaching diversity experience, and a democratic classroom meaningfully harness civic movement and commitment (Merza et al., 2022).

Advantages and Difficulties of having leadership experience as to their Civic Affairs and/or Civic Responsibilities

As student leaders with the underlying civic affairs that they get to participate in and civic responsibilities to which they are liable to fulfill as far as they are concerned and revealed in the results and prior discussion of this study, there is also the need to know what are the advantages they enjoy and difficulties they faced and consider in having such experiences.” One participant even stated that “...it will allow me to gain better knowledge and skills in handling and engaging in the community (Participant 4, personal communication, June 12, 2023).” With this, leadership experiences have helped in learning transferable skills like communication, people skills, teamwork, etc., along with enabling change in perception through experiential learning (Gowthaman, 2019). Additionally, a participant expressed, “...one of the benefits is personal growth because I believe that having the leadership experiences often foster personal growth and self-discovery and since I start joining leadership activities, I had a deeper understanding of my strengths, weaknesses, and passions (Participant 10, personal communication, June 12, 2023).” As for the advantages, most answers of the participants are able ‘to see and be aware of the problems and activities in the community and create a mechanism to address the issues and concerns of the people and the community itself.

On the other hand, they revealed their difficulties to which ‘time conflict’ is the leading answer of the participants and one of them even said “...leadership roles are demanding, sometimes, I lost some of my time for my family and myself. I know that balancing my responsibilities can be challenging, especially if I have limited resources or face competing priorities.” This also shows the difficulty in weighing priorities between position and family. Moreover, a participant expressed, “In leading for sure we can’t please everyone and mostly open for criticisms, which is not good for mental health. Because sometimes I take those criticisms personally and like a big deal (Participant 4, personal communication, June 12, 2023).” Supplemented by Gowthaman (2019) the experiences we have are shaped and influenced by the people we experience it with. In leading people, it is impossible to please everyone especially when everyone has their own opinion and side to express.

These advantages and difficulties with people played an important role in each participant’s experience contributing to their learning in their experience in one way or another. Nevertheless, the role of student leaders both in school and community has a significant impact and contributes more to the growth of society as well as to

the organizations where they act and use it as stepping stones and training grounds for much larger and wider leadership.

CONCLUSION

Active participation of student leaders in civic affairs is seen in this study where they are willing to render their service, exert effort, and impart something positive and beneficial to everyone not only on the school ground but also to the community where they live. Whereas data gathered shows that nine out of ten participants engaged themselves in civic affairs like voting and volunteering, under it, student leaders involved themselves in environmental-related affairs and people's organizations inside their respective local areas as well as actively applying their leadership experiences to the community. Moreover, there may be some advantages/benefits, and difficulties/ challenges that they encounter along the way in leading people however the very end point of this is their action is marked by passionate support for a cause.

Nonetheless, in deepening and expanding community participation, the importance of community affairs has become pivotal for well-functioning. The presence of community and government institutions makes their leadership skills effective and an opportunity for them to hone. Hence, community participation is not only desirable but necessary and viable as it is likely to lead to more equitable, sustainable public community service and improve the livability of their respective local community.

REFERENCES

- Arcega, I. B. (2017). Student leader's volunteerism: Reviving the Bayanihan spirit. *CAPSU Research Journal*, 29(1), 10-25.
- Ayaya, G. (2020). Equipping students for leadership through community engagement. *Sage Journals*, 24(3).
- Chai, M. (2015). Personality and leadership qualities among student leaders. *American Journal of Applied Psychology*, 4(3), 27-32.
- Chitiga, M. (2014). Performing arts for effective civic engagement: Developing creative civically engaged student leaders. *International Journal of Civic Engagement and Social Change*, 1(3), 59-74.
- Clement, R., Deering, M., Mikhael, R., & Garcia, C. (2014). Youth civic engagement and leadership. Washington, D.C.: Hartland Publications.
- Cho, A. (2020). Digital civic engagement by young people. *United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF)*.
- Cui, S., Wu, Q., & Erdemir, B. (2022). Being a college student leader boosts career prospects: A panel survey in China. *Education and Training*, 64(5).
- Lee, B., Liu, K., Samuel, T., Kim, M., & Skett, S. (2022). Students leading students: A qualitative study exploring a student-led model for engagement with the sustainable development goals. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*.
- Matkin, G., Headrick, J., & Sunderman, H. (2023). Developing human potential. *University of Nebraska System*. <https://pressbooks.nebraska.edu/developinghumanpotential/front-matter/editor-information/>
- McBath, G. L. (2019). Students in civic engagement. Charles Town, United States: American Military University.
- Meer, J., Skalicky, J., & Speed, H. (2019). "I didn't just want a degree": Students' perceptions about benefits from participation in student leadership programmes. *The Journal of Leadership Education*, 18(1), 25-44.
- Merza, C., Baga, P., Bautista, P., Bulatao, A., & Pangngay, J. (2022). Pakikipagkapwa: Pathways in developing civic engagement among student leaders. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 5, 61-72.

- Mustapha, M., Baharum, N., Aishah, S., & Pauzi, N. (2016). To serve or not to serve: Student leaders, community service, and community service learning. *Regional Conference on Science, Technology and Social Sciences*, 191-201.
- Mydin, F., & Amran, M. (2019). Socially responsible leadership capacity among student leaders. *Scientific Research and Academic Publisher*, 10(12).
- Nartea, M. (2016). Impact of leadership skills on the student organizational performance of PUP-Paranaque Campus. *European Academic Research*, 4(8).
- Olayinka, A., & Olorunda, S. (2019). Civic knowledge and attitude as determinants of students' civic engagement in secondary school in Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 7(4), 124-128.
- Posner, B. Z. (2018). Effectively measuring student leadership. *Administrative Science Journal*, 221-234.
- Posner, B. Z., & Brodsky, B. (2015). Leadership practices of effective student leaders. *NASPA Journal*, 113-120.
- Santos, J., Ac-ac, C., Dela Cruz, L., Ramos, M., & Villafuerte, M. (2019). Right to vote: Students' involvement in student government elections. Bulacan: Social Science Research Network.
- Sessa, V., Morgan, B., Kalenderli, S., & Hammond, F. (2014). Key events in student leaders' lives and lessons learned from them. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 13(2).